

PECULIARITIES IN THE STRUCTURAL STRUCTURE OF ABŪ BAKR AL-KĀSĀNĪ'S WORK "BADĀ'Ī' AL-ŞANĀ'Ī' FĪ TARTĪB AL-SHARĀ'Ī'"

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ABSTRACT

The opinions expressed in the article are formulated in accordance with the requirements of the methodological principles and traditional methods of the Ḥanafī faith. Opinions on social welfare are observed on the basis of modern standards based on the book "Badā'ī' al-şanā'ī' fī tartīb al-sharā'ī'" written by the jurist of Samarkand, Abū Bakr al-Kāsānī, and based on the jurisprudence rules and legal arguments introduced in Central Asia in general, in particular in our Republic.

Key words: Badā'ī', Şanā'ī', Kāsān, farḍ, wajib, sunnah, evidence, ijmā', qiyās, asl, 'Uşūl, furu', permissible, Islām, sharī'ah.

Abū Bakr al-Kāsānī's work "Badā'ī' al-şanā'ī'" begins with "Kitāb al-Ṭahārah" (Book of Purity) and ends with "Kitāb al-Qarḍ" (Book of Borrowing and Giving).

This work contains a total of seven hundred and eighty (780) chapters and seventy one (71) books. In the work, issues related to such topics as "Inheritance", "Marriage", "Pension" (social security), "Trade", "Boghism", "Jihad" are discussed in detail. The main methodological advantage of the work is that the Shari'a issues are sorted and classified in it.

Abū Bakr ibn Mas'ūd al-Kāsānī, in the preface of the work "Badā'ī' al-şanā'ī'", dwells on the main purpose of writing it and the relevance of writing this work:

"Until now, there are many works of our masters in this field (fiqh), and all of them have written excellent and useful books. However, they did not pay much attention to the classification and classification of Shariah rulings. Only Muḥammad ibn 'Aḥmad ibn Abū 'Aḥmad Samarqandi (may Allah have mercy on him) paid attention to this work, the teacher - inheritor and spreader of the Sunnah, sheikh, ascetic imām, 'Alā' al-Dīn, chairman of the people of the Sunnah. I also followed my teacher and took his example. The main goal of a book written in any field is to provide readers with the information they are looking for in an easy way and bring them closer to the essence of the subject. This goal

is achieved by skillfully sorting and classifying data based on the nature of the fields. Sorting is the careful examination of matters by parts, fragments, and types, and judgment based on rules and criteria. In this way, they are easier to understand and remember, and the work can become a constant source of reference. Paying attention to this, I have collected jurisprudential information in these two books (volumes) according to the order specific to the field (fiqh). I named my book "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i' fī tartīb al-sharā'i'" in order to be worthy of its name, because the work is an example of artistic skill in arrangement and systematization. I ask Allah Almighty to help me finish this book. Hoping for God's favor and grace, I ask Him to keep my book as a source for passing on the legacy of the past teachers to the next generation, and for me to keep it as a memory in this world and in the hereafter. Indeed, He is the Fulfiller of hopes and the granter of requests!"¹

Allama al-Kāsānī also dwells on the fact that in "Muqaddimah" he touches the work on the science of jurisprudence:

"Knowing Allah and knowing His attributes, the greatest science after the science of monotheism is the science of jurisprudence. Fiqh is the science of halal and haram, sharia and rules. All the prophets were sent to convey these orders of Allah. Because a person cannot find the right way without knowing the divine commands, only with the mind. Allah Almighty says: "He gives wisdom to whom He wills." He who has been given wisdom has been given much good."² In some interpretations, it is said that the word "hikmat" refers to the science of jurisprudence. It is narrated from the Messenger of Allah, may God bless him and grant him peace: He said: "Among the prayers to Allah, there is no better deed than the knowledge of jurisprudence." A single scholar who understands religion is a stronger enemy to the devil than a thousand monuments.

There are countless messages promoting the study of this science"³. It is narrated that a person from Sham came to the presence of 'Umar - Madinai Munawwara. When "Umar ibn al-Khaṭṭāb asked: "Why did you come?", he replied: "I came to study Tashahhud well." Then 'Umar cried, even his beard became wet from his tears, then he said: "By Allah, I hope from God that He will never punish you."

The work is called in Arabic "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i' fī tartīb al-sharā'i'" and it is translated into Uzbek as "Fine arts in the arrangement of Shariah matters". But it

¹ Alā' al-Dīn Abū Bakr ibn Mas'ūd al-Kāsānī. Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i' fī tartīb al-sharā'i' (checked and explained by Sheikh Ali Muḥammad and Sheikh 'Ādil 'Aḥmad 'Abd al-Majīd). - Lebanon: Dor al-kutub al-ilmiyya, 1997 (ten volumes). (hereinafter: Al-Kāsānī. Badā'i'). – V: I. – P.88.

² Sūrah Al-Baqarah verse 269.

³ Al-Kāsānī. Badā'i' . V: I – P. 87.

is difficult to say that this translation was able to fully reflect the content of the text. This translation has been used for many years. Nevertheless, as a result of the lexical analysis of the words in the name of the work, it would be better if the phrase "artistic skill" was used instead of the phrase "fine arts" in the title, because the meaning of "artistic skill" has priority in the semantics of the phrase "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i' fī tartīb al-sharā'i'" in the Arabic language. In this case, the title of the work can be translated into Uzbek as "artistic skill in arranging the laws of Sharia".

Until now, there are various debates among scholars about whether "Badā'i'" is a commentary or not a commentary on "Tuḥfat al-fuqahā". According to some scholars, it is a commentary.⁴

Dr. Muḥammad Zaki Abdulbar, who carried out a critical edition of "Tuḥfat al-fuqahā" in 1959, al-Kāsānī also says that based on the fact that the information in "Tuḥfat al-fuqahā" is also included in "Badā'i'" in the same form, this work can be considered a commentary on "Tuḥfat al-fuqahā"⁵. The research scientist Hefenin expressed a concluding opinion that "It is not a commentary on "Tuḥfat al-fuqahā", but a classification that mimics it⁶." There are cases of support for both opinions among scientists.

Oriental scholar Otto Shpiz believes that calling the work a commentary on "Tuḥfat al-fuqahā" is wrong and unfair to the author.⁷

In the preface to the work, al-Kāsānī stated that he followed his teacher in terms of style, but nowhere in the work did he say that it was a commentary on "Tuḥfat". "Tuḥfat" and its author are hardly mentioned in the work. In the work, the author mainly mentions the work of Imām Muḥammad (d. 189/805) "Zāhir al-riwāyah".

For example, at the beginning of Kitāb ul-Ghasb, he said that Imām Muḥammad (d. 189/805) had researched the issues related to usurpation and loss under this topic, and he himself approached this topic in this way⁸. Although this systematically classified work follows "Tuḥfat" in terms of style, it is considered that it is far ahead of "Tuḥfat" in terms of artistry in covering the topics.

Consequently, when comparing the work "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i'" with the work "Tuḥfat al-fuqahā", Al-Kāsānī uses the analytical method of interpretation,

⁴ Ḥājjī Khalīfa. Kashf al-zunūn, – V: I. – P.230-371.; Qurashi. Jawāhir al-muḍīyah. – V: IV. – P. 26.

⁵ 'Alā' al-Dīn Samarqandī. Tuḥfat al-fuqahā' (Muḥammad Zaki Abdulbar prepares for publication). – Dasmascus: 1377/1958

⁶ Heffening, "Kāsānī" IA.VI. 374.

⁷ Otto Spies, "Istanbul Handschriften zu dem Rechtswerk Bada'i' us-Sana'i' des Kasani", Isl., XLI (1969).

⁸ Al-Kāsānī. Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i'. – V: I. – P. 3.

which is acceptable and understandable to everyone, in interpreting jurisprudential issues and rulings. The scientist, citing the text of "Tuḥfat", does not begin to interpret and interpret it, but uses an independent analytical method from beginning to end.

Fadwa 'Abd Al-'Alīm 'Aḥmad At-Tayyari quotes Imām Ibn 'Ābidīn's assessment of this work of Imām Al-Kāsānī and adds: "Imām Ibn 'Ābidīn al-Ḥanafī said about this book: "This book is of great importance. There is no equal among our books."⁹ 'Aḥmad al-Tayyari's next words prove that it would not be correct to say that when Imām Ibn 'Ābidīn meant our books, he meant only the books that existed before Al-Kāsānī's "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i'" work."¹⁰ These words of the scholars show the high value of the work "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i'" among the Muslim jurisprudential heritage.

Based on the experiences of jurists and scholars before him, Al-Kāsānī focuses on the importance of jurisprudence as a point of reference in the analysis and clarification of jurisprudential issues in his work "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i'". It can be seen that the scholar used jurisprudence rules effectively in the following cases:

1) After presenting the views of the parties on controversial issues, justifying the results of the Ḥanafī school; Example: On the question of the permissibility of wine and pork for dhimmis, Ḥanafī jurists justify their view with the rule "The original ruling in staying (continuing) is itlaq".¹¹

2) Advocating the final result of the sect in a matter; For example, in the Book of Nikah, he answers the objection to the Ḥanafī Madhhab's view that dowry is a condition for the permissibility of marriage through another rule: "In such a situation, there is no conflict between our rules."¹²

3) In the event that a court judge thinks that a significant part of an issue has been concluded, it means that this judgment will be fulfilled; "In rulings about many, many parts replace the whole", "If ijtiḥad contradicts the text, it is invalid."¹³

4) In showing that the judgments given on various subjects are based on the original rules and that there is no conflict and difference between these rules; That is, "Different opinions on this subject are based on the following

⁹Ibn Obidin hoshiyasi. 1-juz' 100-b. (١٠٠١) حاشية ابن عابدين.

¹⁰ Fadwa 'Abd Al-'Alīm 'Aḥmad At-Tayyari. Corrections in the book "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i'" by Imām Al-Kāsānī. (From the beginning of the Book of Hunting to the end of the Book of Atonements), magister. work - Umul Qura University. 2007. E-mail: faadwa@gmail.com

¹¹ al-Kāsānī. Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i'. – V:X. – P.21.

¹² Al-Kāsānī. Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i'. – V:III. – P.485.

¹³ Al-Kāsānī. Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i'. – V:5. – P.52-3.

principle; According to Imām Shāfi'ī, the limit of qazf is the right of an impartial servant. According to the rule based on our companions, the rights of Allah and the servant are considered to exist together in Qazf."¹⁴

5) Shar'an eliminates the view that what is forbidden does not have a legal effect; "(something) that is not mashroo' is not taken into consideration in terms of judgment".¹⁵

6) Commenting on the interpretations of Ḥanafī mujtahid jurists on various topics; "The word is the word of Amin with an oath." "It is true that what each person does is for himself and not for others"¹⁶.

7) Analyzing the opinions of the Ḥanafī jurists on the issues on which they disagreed, and choosing one of them as the preferred one; Shar'an states that it is more appropriate to accept the view of Abū Ḥanīfa citing the rule that "what is false is equal to what is not true".¹⁷

8) Criticizing views that he disagrees with by bringing up various ideological differences within the sect;

Explains that the statute of limitations precludes testimony under the rule that "judgment depends not on wisdom, but on clear reason".¹⁸

9) If there are places based on intellectual arguments in the issues, in interpreting them; He mentions the rule "Responsibility that does not tolerate is impossible" in explaining the intellectual argument he gave to prove the matter..¹⁹

10) Commenting on narrative evidences (narratives) based on jurisprudential rulings, characterizing them and describing their flaws. For example; The Qur'ān explains the prescribed amount of "mash" in the verse "wash your head²⁰..." through the rule "The whole judgment is executed on many parts"²¹.

11) In quoting narrations narrated from the Companions as evidence and interpreting these narrations; When explaining the views of the Ḥanafī sect, he mentions the ijma of the companions, and when explaining that ijma, he cites the rule "The absolute is spread over the perfect".²²

¹⁴ Al-Kāsānī.Badā'i'ī. – V: IX. – P.242.

¹⁵ Al-Kāsānī.Badā'i'ī. – V: IV. – P.206-7.

¹⁶ Al-Kāsānī.Badā'i'ī. – V: VIII. – P.330.

¹⁷ Al-Kāsānī.Badā'i'ī. – V: X. – P.183-4.

¹⁸ Al-Kāsānī.Badā'i'ī. – V: I. – P.507.; – V: III. – P.575; – V: IX. – P.56.; – V: X. – P.332.

¹⁹ Al-Kāsānī.Badā'i'ī. – V: I. – P.552-3.

²⁰ Moida,5/6.

²¹ Al-Kāsānī.Badā'i'ī. – V: I. – P.103.

²² Al-Kāsānī.Badā'i'ī. – V: VIII. – P.99.

12) When citing the opinions of jurists on these issues in subjects that do not rely on direct nass (narrative evidence); Under the contract, if there is a person who gives permission, it is invalid if he gives permission, and if it is not given, it cannot be invalid due to permission that is likely to be given later, he cites the rule "What is not proven by clear evidence cannot be proven by doubt".²³

13) Emphasizing that this issue is based on this rule in specific examples; In *Zāhir al-riwāyah*, commenting on the ruling that the intention of a person who says "you are free" to his wife with the intention of divorce is not authentic, he emphasizes that this ruling is based on the rule "The ruling that is established due to necessity is determined by the amount of necessity"²⁴.

14) While citing the views of various fiqh schools and Ḥanafī jurists, explaining the vices and conditions of the judgments they gave; It mentions the rule that "subsequently granted permission replaces previously granted authority"²⁵ or "Contracts pay attention to meaning, not word forms."²⁶

15) In explaining differences between jurisprudential issues that are different in terms of judgment despite being similar in form; Reminds of the rule "The intention is ignored if it is not accompanied by a verb (action)".²⁷

Or: Explaining that the fasting person's doubts about the sunrise and sunset are different in terms of their effect on fasting, he cites the rule "A deed done with faith does not become invalid because of a deed with doubt".²⁸

16) *In the sense that there is some rule that is overlooked and the judgment is based on that rule; For example: "A yaqin does not disappear because of doubt"²⁹, "Imali (action)³⁰ of the word is better than neglect (abandonment)", "Baqa (continuation of action) is easier than initiation (beginning)³¹", "It is determined according to the amount of needs"³², "Bayina (document) to the claimant, and the oath to the denier"³³ and so on.*

²³ Al-Kāsānī. *Badā'i'*. – V: VI.

²⁴ Al-Kāsānī. *Badā'i'*. – V: IV. – P. 226.

²⁵ Al-Kāsānī. *Badā'i'*. – V: II. – P. 396-7.

²⁶ Al-Kāsānī. *Badā'i'*. – V: VIII. – P. 6.

²⁷ Al-Kāsānī. *Badā'i'*. – V: II. – P. 396-7.

²⁸ Al-Kāsānī. *Badā'i'*. – V: II. – P. 634.

²⁹ Al-Kāsānī. *Badā'i'*. – V: I. – P. 278-9, 359, 378-9, 402, 600.; – V: II. – P. 166, 607, 633-4.; – V: III. – P. 294; – V: IV. – P. 273, 304, 398, 481; – V: VII. – P. 276; – V: VIII. – P. 501.

³⁰ Al-Kāsānī. *Badā'i'*. – V: I. – P. 121, 169; – V: III. – P. 264.

³¹ Al-Kāsānī. *Badā'i'*. – V: IV. – P. 378.; – V: VIII. – P. 126; – V: IX. – P. 5542.; – V: X. – P. 597.

³² Al-Kāsānī. *Badā'i'*. – V: I. – P. 151; – V: II. – P. 155; – V: IV. – P. 246.

³³ Al-Kāsānī. *Badā'i'*. – V: II. – P. 451-2; – V: IV. – P. 248; – V: V. – P. 283-4; – V: VII. – P. 233; – V: VIII. – P. 70, 74, 75, 256-7, 500, 507; – V: IX. – P. 155; – V: X. – P. 104..

In addition to these, the fact that the essence of the points of reference used and taken as a basis in the clarification of jurisprudential issues within the sect or in inter-sectarian relations is reflected in the following:

Just as the scholar bases the judgment of the sect on the basis of the rules, he also criticizes the approaches of the other side on the disputed topics, sometimes citing evidence from the scriptures, and sometimes directly relying on the rules.³⁴ For example, Imām Shāfi'ī (v.y.204/820) says that in order to prevent the cancellation of the contract due to the loss of quality of the sold goods in the hands of the seller, a prison sentence is applied to the seller. Al-Kāsānī, on the other hand, says that since the event of destruction of goods before the payment of money occurs in very few cases, it is accepted as if it had never happened, and the seller has the right not to be arrested, and he supports his opinion with the rule that "In rare cases, there is no judgment", and Imām Shāfi'ī (v.y.204/ 820) criticizes his opinion.³⁵

Al-Kāsānī not only mentions the rules based on the Ḥanafī madhhab, but also mentions the rules based on the scholars of other madhhabs.³⁶ For example, Imām Shāfi'ī's opinion that a person who breaks his fast by having sexual intercourse several times in Ramadan must pay special expiation for each sexual intercourse according to the rule "The sentence is repeated with the repetition of the reason".³⁷

When Al-Kāsānī discusses the views of other fiqh schools, if there is no conflict between them, he suffices to cite the view and the rule from which it is based. If there is a difference between them, and the reason for this is only due to the difference of the rule on the subject, apart from the nass and ijma, the reason for the difference is stated to be from the rules on which the basis is derived.³⁸

Relying on the rules in disputes shows that the differences are due to the fact that the different approaches to the problem presented are different, and that the judgments are therefore different. He expresses that the conflicting opinions between the Shāfi'īs and the Ḥanafīs regarding the qazf haddi depend on the original rule as follows: That is, "Different opinions on this subject are based on the following original; According to Imām Shāfi'ī, the limit of qazf is the

³⁴ Al-Kāsānī.Badā'i'. – V: I. – P.312-3,348,361; – V: II. – P.50,254-5,420,629; – V:III. – P.78,80; – V: IV. – P.304,307-8; – V: VI. – P.96; – V: VII. – P.161; – V: X. – P.316-317.

³⁵ Al-Kāsānī.Badā'i'. – V: VII. – P.247.

³⁶ Al-Kāsānī.Badā'i'. – V:I. –B.97,191-2,344-5; – V:II. – P.70,392-3,401,416-7,491; – V:III. – P.6-9,80,382-3; – V:IV. – P.34,211,319,382; – V:V. – P.437,493; – V:VI. – P.57,116,550; – V:VII. – P.22,60,453; – V:VIII. – P.118,373; – V:IX. – P.33,513; – V:X. – P.41,404,522.

³⁷ Al-Kāsānī.Badā'i'. – V:II. – P.625.

³⁸ Al-Kāsānī.Badā'i'. – V:IX. – P.332, – V:IX. – P.249,490; – V:X. – P.29,61,522-24.

right of an impartial servant. According to the rule based on our companions, the rights of Allah and the servant are considered to exist together in Qazf.³⁹

Other schools of thought, when presenting controversial issues that reach different conclusions, sometimes refer to the interpretation and field of knowledge of the rule and criticize wrong approaches, rather than merely acknowledging the rule on which they base it.⁴⁰ He also says that he abandoned their views and rules based on them because of nass or ijma' (especially the consensus of the Companions).⁴¹

In cases where the judgments are not stated in the scriptures, while quoting the rules as evidence, many officers make judgments based on the specific rules.⁴² For example: Ḥanafī jurists' debates regarding slave emancipation are based on the authority that "according to Abū Ḥanīfa, slave emancipation is mutajazza' (something that can be divided), but according to Abū Yūsuf and Imām Muḥammad, it is not mutajazza' (cannot be divided)."⁴³

In addition to quoting jurisprudential rules that cause differences of opinion in the analysis of disputed issues, scholars also mention the rules of method.⁴⁴

In the discussion between Imām Shāfi'ī (v.y.204/820) and Imām Ḥanīfa regarding what happens to the thing that is thrown when a stone is thrown at Satan, "It is not accepted as an absolute muqayyad. If it is possible, it is valid on the basis of absolute persuasion and muqayyad on the basis of restriction."⁴⁵

He expresses all the rules as al-Asl, al-Asl al-Ma'hud, az- Zāhir, al-Mazhab, al-Jami' and al-Qiyas and makes judgments based on them.

The scientist cites language rules and uses them as evidence. He interprets the discussion of some jurisprudential issues by relating them to the rules of language.⁴⁶ For example: explaining the conflicting opinions of Ḥanafī jurists regarding the consequences of an oath, he refers to the rules "According to the opinion of linguists, a word used in an absolute sense (among the masses) is accepted in a widespread sense" or "A word uttered in an absolute sense is accepted in its true sense".⁴⁷

³⁹ Al-Kāsānī. Badā'ī'. – V:IX. – P.242.

⁴⁰ Al-Kāsānī. Badā'ī'. – V:I. – P.330-1,360-1,614-5; – V:II. – P.236-7; – V:III. – P.6-9,30,227; – V:IV. – P.206-7,375; – V:VI. – P.241-42; – V:VII. – P. 60-63,453; – V:VIII. – P.94,220,231,235,279 -80,397,468,494; – V: IX. – P.42,190,332; – V:X. – P.39,70,71,193, 203, 356,490.

⁴¹ Al-Kāsānī. Badā'ī'. – V:I. – P.482; – V:III. – P.80; – V:X. – P.321.

⁴² Al-Kāsānī. Badā'ī'. – V:III. – P.49,336,395; – V:IV. – P.282,286,486; – V:V. – P.47,432; – V:VII. – P.475; – V:VIII. – P.231-5,265-66-67,443.

⁴³ Al-Kāsānī. Badā'ī'. – V:V. – P.235,249,284-5,332,346,383-4,451,455.

⁴⁴ Al-Kāsānī. Badā'ī'. – V:III. – P.139.

⁴⁵ Al-Kāsānī. Badā'ī'. – V:III. – P.186,452,607; – V:IV. – P.307-8,4057; – V:V. – P.47,232; – V:VI. – B. 177,186,489, 494; – V:VII. – P.36; – V:VIII. – P.294,302; – V:IX. – P.48,384; – V:X. – P.105.

⁴⁶ Al-Kāsānī. Badā'ī'. – V:III. – P.414; – V:IV. – P.142-3,372; – V:VI. – P.93,96; – V:IX. – P.56.

⁴⁷ Al-Kāsānī. Badā'ī'. – V:IV. – P.139.

Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī, in sorting fiqh issues based on rules, relies first on the opinions of Abū Ḥanīfa (r.a.) and puts the rules based on the scholars of the Ḥanafī school in the first place. The scholars of the Ḥanafī madhhab quote the rules based on "Abū Ḥanīfa says". For example: Abū Ḥanīfa says: "Abandoning a qiyas is done by relying on another qiyas that is stronger than it."

Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī's work "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i' fī tartīb al-sharā'i'" is distinguished by the fact that its structure, topics, chapters and chapters are given in a new order, unlike the classical commentaries written before it.

In short, Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī is a scholar, jurist, who laid the foundation for the tradition of arranging jurisprudence rules in this way, and his formation as a scientific type, as well as a person who mastered poetic and artistic methods perfectly and managed to use them skillfully.